

Impact of HR practices of Woolworths Limited Australia

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Abstract:

This research investigates the A report on HR practices of Woolworths Limited Australia. Data were collected from various secondary sources, ie. Annual reports, magazines and quarterly reports. Data were analyzed by using SPSS-22 version. It was revealed that Employee engagement could be enhanced by various tactics as mentioned earlier by the JD-R model. However, it has been observed that by expanding benefits with respect employee need is beneficial in enhancing their level of engagement. The company is suggested to provide a health bonus to its staff. Along with it, some senior employees with family issues can also be offered health care. It was further revealed that it was found out that the human resource department of the company is highly particular about the work performance of their staff. Since it is a retail company, it is essential for the staff to be trained enough to operate different IT technologies in the store. In this regard, it has been established that Woolworths annually spend a good amount of training and development of their staff to enhance their work performance. The company offers proper training to new staff to make them aware of the working criteria. Moreover, after performance audit, gaps in performances are met by relevant training where necessary. In short, HR management has a strong inclination towards the development needs of its staff.

Introduction

Human resource management holds undeniable importance in the success of a business organisation. This is due to the fact that HR managers empower the employees by providing an inclusive workplace environment and motivates them through different tactics of employee benefits, which ultimately enhances their work progress. It has been observed that a positive organisational culture and employee satisfaction are some of the important job tasks of HR managers in the corporate world (Lawler, 2012). The aim of the present report is to assess the HR practices of a business organisation, i.e., Woolworths Limited. The said company is a leading retailing service provider in Australia. The report is going to analyse its employee performance, culture, and engagement related initiative. In the end, appropriate recommendations will be incorporated.

Discussion

Performance Related Initiatives

In a general perspective, the success factor of business organisations is dependent on the employee enthusiasm in achieving organisational goals. Their enhanced work performance is essential to gain greater business stability. In this regard, the global trend of spending on employee performance is increasing with the passage of time (Lawler, 2015). Considering performance related initiative in Woolworths Company, it was found out that the human resource department of the company is highly particular about the work performance of their staff. Since it is a retail company, it is essential for the staff to be trained enough to operate different IT technologies in the store. In this regard, it has been established that Woolworths annually spend a good amount of training and development of their staff to enhance their work performance. The company offers proper training to new staff to make them aware of the working criteria. Moreover, after a performance audit, gaps in performances are met by relevant training where necessary. In short, HR management has a strong inclination towards the development needs of its staff (Woolworths Holding Limited, 2018). Workplace discrimination between employees while providing training and development opportunities is found to be a common issue in global business organisations. However, Woolworths proclaimed that they offer an equal chance of personal development to their workers. It is to be noted that the company reportedly spend a huge amount on its black employees the same as they do for the native people with no discrimination (Woolworths Holding Limited, 2018).

Figure 1: Spending on employee training to enhance performance (Woolworths Holding Limited, 2018)

The Annual Report of Woolworths (2018) revealed that they strive to deliver a better experience to their customers as well as employees for which they provide interpersonal skill development training to up to 90,000 workers annually. As a result of this annual spending on training and development, the success rate of the company is increasing, which can be measured by its increasing sale, annual revenues, and market share value.

Culture Related Initiatives

Workplace diversity and associated conflicts are a part of the global business environment. To operate successfully, it is essential to consider the needs of both culturally diverse members and native members of the company. Human resource management has to take effective steps to ensure a positive and inclusive workplace environment where every entity is valued. This inclusivity needs to be retained while dealing with diverse customers (Barak, 2016; Paludi, 2012). Considering the culture-based initiative of HR in Woolworths, it was found out that the company has started a diversity program in association with Community Corporate, which aims to offer job opportunities to diverse communities. Specifically, this initiative intends to embrace diversity. Moreover, with the help of this association, the company provide culture-based training sessions which intends to ensure an inclusive work environment with no discrimination. In addition to it, Woolworths is a known business organisation with a greater emphasis on culturally diverse customers. The company trains its staff to be efficient in cross-cultural communication its diverse community of consumers (Annual Report, 2018).

As far as the workplace environment of the company is concerned, it has been established that Woolworths ensures inclusivity in its workplace environment. More Specifically, HR management of the company adopts bias-free recruitment practice where all entities are invited to be a part of a company irrespective of the differences in gender, culture, race, ethnicity, or physical appearance. According to the management of the company, what matters is the intellectual capability and professionalism of a person which make him/her eligible (Woolworths Holding Limited, 2018). In addition, the Annual Report of the company (2018) revealed that Woolworths in the Australian Workplace Equality Index Awards achieved Gold Tier Status in recognition of its initiative of inclusion and embracing diversity. This enables the company to gain a stable market share value and greater employee retention rate which ultimately enhances its annual revenue stream. The company has further set its milestone for supporting refugees and indigenous people in providing employment opportunities until 2020 (Annual, Report, 2018).

Engagement Related Initiatives

In a general perspective, performance appraisals and monetary benefits are said to be the major contributor to the enhanced employee engagement within the firm (Saks, 2014). As per the theoretical underpinning of Job Demands-Resources model (JD-R model), it has been established that there are four levels of resources that are typically associated with job demands of the employees which include work, interpersonal, and organisational. Employees have different needs associated with these mentioned categories as shown in table 1 below. It is said that employee engagement level can be enhanced by fulfilling these needs and by providing a positive and inclusive workplace environment (Saks, 2014).

Table 1: Aspects of the JD-R model and employee job needs

Resource Level	Example
Task	Performance appraisal
Work	Involvement in decision making
Interpersonal	Co-workers and supervisors support
Organisational	Growth and career opportunities

Considering the HR initiative in Woolworths Company to enhance employee engagement, it was observed that the company has well-established remuneration policies. The management perceives that the success of the company is achieved by its people or workers and that they can be rewarded for their efforts. They give market competitive remuneration benefit to its workers. This monetary benefit or performance bonus enhances their work performance and job satisfaction (Marcelo-Jones, 2009). In addition, the working environment in the company is inclusive as established earlier where every entity is valued and given equal chance of expressing their viewpoints. This involvement of the employees in the company also improves employee motivation and engagement. Other than this, the management and senior workers support other workers, which ultimately enhance the work experience and expertise of co-workers. In short, the entire working environment is inclusive and supportive. To create growth and career development opportunities for its staff, the company arrange talent planning session where the management discuss performances and related growth of the of employees in terms of job designation and monetary terms as well (Annual Report, 2018).

Conclusion

The purpose of this report was to analyse the HR strategies of a selected organisation. Specifically, the report incorporated Woolworth's HR practices, such as how the company improves work performance, organisation culture, and employee engagement level. The main findings of the paper revealed that Woolworths offers training and development opportunities to enhance work performance. The organisational culture of the company is inclusive, and they promote cultural diversity to empower diverse employees. Lastly, the company offers performance appraisals and bonuses to enhance employee engagement in the company. These strategies ultimately enhance its employee satisfaction level, annual revenue stream, and market share value.

Recommendations

• Performance-related recommendation

It is to be noted that the performance of the employees can be enhanced by giving them a chance to discuss their work-related issues and skill gaps. This strategy would specifically address their individual needs rather than the attending training programs of the tasks they are already aware of (Bhattacharyya, 2011). Woolworths Company is very particular in terms of employee performance. However, all their initiatives are company oriented. Thus, the company is suggested to take the initiative from the perspective of the employees specifically. For this purpose, they can create a poll or a survey which enables every entity to express their skill gap. Ultimately on the basis of this employee survey, appropriate training and development sessions can be scheduled.

• Culture-related recommendation-Culture is an integral part of a society and even in

Business organisations as its stability are said to be a major contributor to the positivity in the workplace environment which encourages workers and boost their self-esteem (Ashkanasy, 2011). Woolworths has string inclination towards diversity and respects individual differences. However, it is suggested to consider the different cultural beliefs of the workers. More specifically, the company can offer off days to the culturally diverse people during their festival days with monetary funds. This would further promote inclusivity and cultural diversity within the workplace environment. Facility to their families as well. This initiative would motivate the workers to perform efficiently. Ultimately their engagement with organisational goals would be enhanced.

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